

OPTIMUS

Optimising energy use in cities through a smart decision support system

The **OPTIMUS** project is devising, developing and delivering a Decision Support System (DSS) integrated in an advanced ICT platform, to help local authorities to achieve significant reductions of energy consumption and CO₂ emissions in their buildings.

The **OPTIMUS** DSS will be tested in three municipalities across Europe:

- **Savona**, ITALY
- **Sant Cugat del Vallès**, SPAIN
- **Zaanstad**, THE NETHERLANDS

PARTNERS

National Technical University of Athens
GREECE. Project coordinator

LaSalle ARQ
ARC Engineering and Architecture
La Salle Campus Barcelona
SPAIN

I.C.L.E.I.
Local Governments for Sustainability
Iclei European Secretariat GMBH
GERMANY

Fundación Tecnalía
Research & Innovation
SPAIN

Politecnico di Torino
ITALY

D'Appolonia S.p.A.
ITALY

Università Degli Studi Di Genova
ITALY

Comune di Savona
ITALY

Sense One Technologies
GREECE

Gemeente Zaanstad
THE NETHERLANDS

Ajuntament de Sant Cugat del Vallès
SPAIN

CONTACT

ARC Engineering and Architecture La Salle
Quatre Camins 2
08022 Barcelona
SPAIN

info@optimus-smartcity.eu
arc@salleurl.edu

www.optimus-smartcity.eu

OPTIMUS

Optimising energy use in cities through a smart decision support system

This project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Programme for Research, Technological Development and Demonstration under Grant Agreement N°. 608703

